

The Vital Role of Insects in Soil Health: Guardians of Earth's Living Cradle

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Introduction:

Soil, often referred to as the "skin of the Earth," is a complex and dynamic ecosystem that sustains life in myriad ways. Beneath its surface lies a bustling world of microorganisms, plant roots, and, crucially, insects. This article delves into the indispensable role of insects in maintaining soil health, exploring their diverse functions and the symbiotic relationships that make them the unsung heroes of our terrestrial environments. Soil residing insect diversity, distribution and richness are determined by several factors such which includes organic matter content, soil features, cover vegetation, soil disturbance (mechanical soil tillage), fire, and pollution. Moreover, the diverse taxa respond in a different way to a variety of prevailing environmental factors. Some groups are more sensitive and their population fluctuates with slight changes in degree of features available to their surroundings², while others are profuse and more able to react to soil degradation. In addition, different species belonging to the same taxonomic group can respond differently. As it is known, the Acari and Collembola are the two major groups which are generally considered in soil quality evaluation approach. Some other groups, such as Coleoptera, Diptera and Araneae, are often elaborate in studies aimed to estimate soil health/quality/degradation/pollution, while other groups, usually Symphyla, Pauropoda, Pseudoscorpionida and others, are normally little discussed in soil quality monitoring or conferred together with other soil arthropods taxa.

1. Decomposition and Nutrient Cycling:

One of the primary contributions of insects to soil health lies in their ability to decompose organic matter. Insects such as beetles, ants, and larvae play a pivotal role in breaking down dead plant material, releasing essential nutrients back into the soil. This process,

known as nutrient cycling, is vital for sustaining plant growth and overall ecosystem health. Insects, with their amazing diversity and adaptableness, are significant players in this crucial process. In the woods when the plants shed their leaves, animals die, or other organic material decays, scavenger insects dive in to feast on these fragments. They breakdown the complex organic molecules into simpler forms, liberating nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus back into the soil. Termites contribute actively to soil turnover, and the contribution of termite and mounds of several species of ant to soil turnover is a regular and never ending process which adds several factors to soil. Termite mounds can persevere in the landscape for more than two decades, while ant mound durability varies from weeks to even decades. Ants and termites directly involved two different services they either increase infiltration by improving soil structure and porosity, or to decrease infiltration by producing compact surfaces which assist runoff and erosion. Additional effects include the chemical adjustment of the soil profile by ants and termites gathering and moving live and dead animal and plant materials to their nest structures, and by the additions of excretions and excreta in nest construction. The majority of ants and termites known to increase C and other nutrient levels, especially N, P and K, as well as exchangeable Mg and Ca.

2. Soil Aeration and Structure:

Burrowing insects and earthworms are good architects of soil structure. Their habit of constant tunnelling improves soil aeration, allowing oxygen to reach plant roots and promoting the movement of water and nutrients. The intricate network of tunnels created by these soil engineers improves soil structure, preventing compaction and facilitating the absorption of water. Insects known to improve soil porosity thus provide adequate aeration and improve the water-holding capacity of soil, also facilitate root penetration, and prevent surface crusting and erosion of topsoil.

3. Pest Control and Soil Protection:

Certain insects act as natural predators, keeping pest populations in check and contributing to the overall balance of the soil ecosystem. Various species of rove beetles, predatory ground beetles, soil nesting hymenopterans, oribatids, ants and plentiful spiders help control the populations of harmful insects, protecting both plants and the soil from potential threats.

4. Pollination and Plant Interaction:

While the role of insects in pollination is often associated with flowers, some insects play a crucial role in soil-based pollination. Beetles, for instance, pollinate plants that lack showy flowers, contributing to the reproduction of a variety of plant species. Various soil

dwelling insects and spiders are known to contribute in pollination, various soil nest builder hymenopteran are actively involved in pollination to the vegetation nearby as well as the role of rove beetles and ground beetles cannot be ignored in pollination. This interaction is essential for maintaining biodiversity and ensuring the health of both soil and vegetation.

5. Soil Biodiversity:

Insects are key players in the intricate web of soil biodiversity. The insects are the crucial members in soil food web insects alone comprises a significant portion of diverse fauna in soil biodiversity, the ability to thrive in various degraded soil as well as eroded land make insects a good candidate as bio indicator since their presence and quantities are extensively used to uncover various soil physical property. Their presence influences the diversity and abundance of other soil organisms, creating a dynamic ecosystem where each component plays a unique role. A rich insect community reflects a healthy and balanced soil environment.

6. Adaptation to Urban Environments:

As urbanization continues to reshape landscapes, certain insects adapt and thrive in urban soil environments. Studying these adaptable species can provide insights into sustainable practices that balance the needs of human development with the preservation of soil health and biodiversity.

Conclusion:

Insects are the unsung guardians of soil health, orchestrating a symphony of interactions that sustain life beneath our feet. Recognizing their multifaceted roles in decomposition, nutrient cycling, pest control, pollination, and soil structure is crucial for fostering sustainable agricultural practices and preserving the delicate balance of our planet's living cradle. As we delve deeper into the intricacies of soil- insect relationships, we unveil the remarkable tapestry of life that flourishes in the hidden realm beneath our feet, reminding us that the health of our soil is intrinsically linked to the well-being of the entire ecosystem.

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